

Final Report

STORAGE AND COMPUTE WORKFLOW COST COMPARISONS

Stephen Bird
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Project summary

Storage and compute infrastructure provide a fundamental foundation underpinning research workflows across Australia. Institutions and research organisations are rightly exploring and assessing commercial services versus nationally subsidised services against a range of criteria, including service quality, service capabilities, and total cost of ownership. Through the ARDC Compute and Storage Discovery Activity program, QCIF has undertaken a comparison of representative storage and compute workflows across QRIScloud and AWS.

Findings

The key findings from this project are:

1. Independent of quality of service factors, depending on the workload and implementation choices, costs for commercial services can range from being on parity with QRIScloud services through to being twenty (20) times the cost
2. Scale is needed in order to be cost effective, but too much scale may result in wasted resources
3. Aggregation can reduce duplication of effort and deliver operational cost savings
4. There is a place for commercial cloud services in supporting research workloads
5. If transitioning to commercial cloud services, workloads should ideally be converted or re-architected where possible to minimise recurring costs
6. Many commercial cloud costs are obfuscated, making it difficult to accurately predict costs, however, it is possible to reasonably estimate a minimum base cost to use as a basis of comparison.

Analysis

The importance of scale

Commercial service providers operate at a hyper-scale as a means to minimise the cost of delivering a service unit, whether that be a vCPU hour or a gigabyte of storage. Clearly, there needs to be a balance between the demand for a service unit, the scale required to meet demand, and the price of a service unit in order to determine whether a service should be provided in-house versus in commercial cloud.

If demand for a service is not of sufficient scale, commercial cloud may be more cost effective as the means to deliver the service. If the demand for the service continues to increase, an equilibrium point is reached where the cost of providing the service in-house matches the cost of providing the service through commercial cloud. If there continues to be sufficient demand for a service, the cost savings may reach a scale where it warrants providing the service in-house rather than through commercial cloud. Care needs to be taken when assessing and provisioning for demand, as expanding capacity too far beyond demand leads to the under utilisation of resources, which increases the cost per consumed service unit.

A visual summary of these points is presented in Figure 1. This model would be used in conjunction with a demand curve projection to assess the value of establishing in-house services versus use of commercial cloud.

Storage and compute workflow cost comparisons

Figure 1: Assessing services for in-house infrastructure versus commercial cloud

With a large portion of the total cost of ownership of infrastructure attributable to staffing, the scale factor can be further realised by recognising that, with appropriate processes and automation, one person can just as easily manage 1,000 cores as they can 100 cores, or 1 petabyte as they can 1 terabyte. As a result, increasing the capacity for a service may not require additional staff, allowing that component of the operations cost to be spread over an increased capacity, bringing the overall cost per service unit down. For QRIScloud's cloud computing environment, a scale of 4,000 vCPUs becomes cost competitive against comparable commercial cloud vCPUs. The current scale of QRIScloud's storage infrastructure, before considering commercial costs for ingress and egress of data, provides Frequent Access storage that is 5% of AWS EFS costs and 66% of AWS S3 costs, and Infrequent Access storage that is on par with AWS Glacier. For high-throughput computing, QRIScloud's current scale makes it marginally more expensive than commercial cloud, before commercial cloud storage costs are factored in. If the Awoonga HTC cluster was doubled in size (for which there is demand), the in-house compute costs drop to below commercial cloud costs.

Tightly coupled to the scale of infrastructure is its density. As the density increases, it has a commensurate increase in the size of a failure domain, however, can reduce the physical footprint being managed, potentially reducing data centre charges and the number of staff required, both of which can assist in reducing the overall cost per service unit. For example, QRIScloud's original compute environment from 2012-13 consisted of approximately 4,000 vCPUs, across 4 data centre racks, consuming 40kW of power. Comparing this to QRIScloud's Stage 5 environment from mid-2018, there is approximately 3,500 vCPUs, in a single data centre rack, consuming 10 kW of power. Newer offerings coming to market in the coming months will likely halve this footprint.

Aggregation to deliver cost savings

For QRIScloud, the dominant cost, over a typical 5-year life span of equipment, are the costs associated with people to operate and maintain the environments. It is reasonable to assume this is likely to be the case for each ARDC compute and storage node. By amalgamating and aggregating capacity to fewer nodes, there is potential to reduce duplication of effort and reduce the overall operations costs of the research cloud, further reducing the per service unit cost. This is particularly achievable by leveraging higher density storage and compute infrastructure.

There are political and legislative elements that need to be considered for the practicality of aggregation, particularly in terms of how state-level co-investments could be made into infrastructure that is run in a different state, and how certain data, such as clinical research data, can be stored across jurisdictional boundaries.

Storage and compute workflow cost comparisons

Use of commercial cloud

While commercial cloud can be used for the majority of use cases, cost can quickly become a limiting factor if it is not controlled. However, there remain a range of use cases where the use of commercial cloud can make sense, such as:

- Workloads that require a higher level of uptime than can be presently achieved on the research cloud
- Specialised workloads that currently do not have the demand or scale to warrant establishing them within the research cloud.

Where commercial cloud is used, it is recommended that solutions be architected, deployed, and used in a way that minimises cost as best as possible.

Project outputs

Accompanying materials to this report are available at:

<https://nextcloud.griscloud.org.au/index.php/s/GYdnS8Qg89SWRpn>

Introduction

Storage and compute infrastructure provide a fundamental foundation underpinning research workflows across Australia. In the 6 years following the establishment of nationally subsidised storage and compute infrastructure for eResearch, through the Nectar and RDSI projects, there has been an increasing number of commercial providers emerge, offering a range of services that can support research workflows. Institutions and research organisations are rightly exploring and assessing commercial services versus nationally subsidised services against a range of criteria, including service quality, service capabilities, and total cost of ownership.

Through the ARDC Compute and Storage Discovery Activity program, QCIF successfully proposed a project to complete storage and compute workflow cost comparisons. This report presents the findings, and details the work undertaken by QCIF, for this project.

Project goal

The project's goal is to provide an apples-to-apples comparison for the cost of delivering a selection of representative research workloads across a range of platforms.

Project approach

The approach taken for this project involved:

1. Developing a comprehensive cost model for QRIScloud's compute, storage, and high throughput computing services, building on QCIF's earlier cost models.
2. Revising QCIF's existing model for translating the costs of QRIScloud workloads into AWS workloads.
3. Costing representative research workloads, using the updated models, running on both QRIScloud and AWS.

QCIF's QRIScloud cost model

Infrastructure components

QCIF's QRIScloud provides a range of infrastructure and services to support research workloads and use cases.

From a capital perspective, QRIScloud's infrastructure can be broadly separated into the following components:

- Cloud Computing
- Frequent Access Storage
- Infrequent Access Storage
- High Throughput Computing
- Network.

From an operations perspective, QRIScloud is exposed to:

- Data centre charges, such as power consumption, rack charges, and floor space charges
- Staffing costs
- Equipment maintenance.

From a total cost perspective, QRIScloud is conscious of national and local co-contributions that need to be factored into an overall cost-model, such as:

- Nectar Core Services
- Distributed Help Desk
- Co-investment of tape library infrastructure (tape libraries, tape drives, tape media) from The University of Queensland and the Queensland Brain Institute.
- Co-investment of compute nodes by the Global Change Institute and the Queensland Facility for Advanced Bioinformatics.

Cost model

Through this project QCIF has built on its earlier work of establishing cost models for its services. In developing the updated cost model, a building block approach was taken, so as to allow for variations in configurations and quantities of a configuration. Future configurations can be modelled to determine changes in the cost per service unit.

Based on current capacity, QRIScloud's total cost per service unit are:

- | | |
|--|---------|
| • Cloud Computing (vCPU hour with 100GB volume): | \$0.037 |
| • Frequent Access Storage (TB-month): | \$19.44 |
| • Infrequent Access Storage (TB-month): | \$4.91 |
| • High Throughput Computing (core hour with shared scratch space): | \$0.081 |

The cost model that has been developed is available for download at the following link:

<https://nextcloud.qriscloud.org.au/index.php/s/GYdnS8Qg89SWRpn>

QCIF's method for determining AWS costs

Summary

Through this project, QCIF has updated its approach for estimating the base unit costs for equivalent AWS services.

The estimate of equivalent AWS costs for QRIScloud services are:

- Cloud Computing (vCPU hour with no volume): \$0.072
- Frequent Access Storage (TB-month): \$491.52
- Infrequent Access Storage (TB-month): \$73.72
- High-throughput Computing (core hour with no shared scratch space): \$0.0658

Currency conversion

AWS costs have been converted to Australian dollars using a US to Australian currency conversion rate of 0.750. The selected conversion rate introduces a 1.333 multiplier on the published AWS US-dollar costs.

Service mapping

The process QCIF follows involves finding, as close as possible, a like-for-like AWS service that maps to a QRIScloud or national research cloud service so that Members' consumption can be equated, with a cost estimate derived. This is presented below for each service.

Collection storage

QCIF's collection storage services, both Frequent and Infrequent access, present file systems for researcher access. The equivalent AWS service is the Elastic File Service (EFS), catering for both frequent access and infrequent access data. The at-rest cost for storage in AWS EFS is shown in Table 1.

AWS Storage Service	At-rest cost per GB/month (US\$)	At-rest cost per GB/month (AUD\$)
EFS Standard	0.360	0.480
EFS Infrequent Access	0.054	0.072

Table 1: Base cost per GB-month to apply in determining AWS collection storage estimate

Cloud computing

QCIF's cloud computing services, as part of the national research cloud, provides virtual machine instances with built-in storage allocations for root and ephemeral drives. The equivalent services within AWS is the On-Demand Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2).

QCIF's approach has been refined to eliminate the mismatch between Nectar flavours and AWS flavours. QCIF distils the AWS flavour class to its base cost per virtual CPU (vCPU) hour, which is the same value irrespective of the specific flavour used within the flavour class. QCIF selects the EBS-only variants of flavours within a flavour class for this calculation, as these match the characteristics of Nectar instances.

Based on the compute nodes QCIF acquired during the 2018 NCRIS re-refresh, the matching AWS flavour class are the m5a instances. The base cost per vCPU for the EBS-only m5a flavour class is shown in Table 2.

Storage and compute workflow cost comparisons

AWS Flavour	vCPUs	RAM (GiB)	EC2 Cost per hour (US\$)	EC2 Base cost per vCPU hour (US\$)	EC2 Base cost per vCPU hour (AUD\$)
m5a.large	2	8	0.108	0.054	0.072
m5a.xlarge	4	16	0.216	0.054	0.072
m5a.2xlarge	8	32	0.432	0.054	0.072
m5a.4xlarge	16	64	0.864	0.054	0.072
m5a.12xlarge	48	192	2.592	0.054	0.072
m5a.24xlarge	96	384	5.184	0.054	0.072

Table 2: Base cost per GB-month to apply in determining AWS cloud compute estimate

Volume storage

QCIF's volume storage services, which are used in conjunction with cloud computing, present persistent block storage devices that can be attached to a virtual machine instance. The equivalent service within AWS is the Elastic Block Storage (EBS) service. The provisioned cost for storage in AWS EBS is shown in Table A3.

AWS Storage Service	Provisioned cost per GB/month (US\$)	Provisioned cost per GB/month (AUD\$)
EBS General Purpose	0.12	0.16

Table 3: Base cost per GB-month to apply in determining AWS volume storage estimate

High-throughput computing

QCIF's high-throughput compute environment is the Awoonga cluster. The Awoonga cluster uses Intel Broadwell processors, while the AWS c5 flavour class use newer generation Intel Skylake processors. To account for performance difference between the processors the AWS EC2 Compute Units of the On-Demand AWS c5 and the On-Demand AWS c4 flavour classes can be used to calculate a scaling factor. This approach is shown in Table 4, with a scaling factor of 0.8889 selected.

AWS c5 flavour	ECU	AWS c4 flavour	ECU	c4 ECU / c5 ECU
c5.large	9	c4.large	8	0.8889
c5.xlarge	17	c4.xlarge	16	0.9412
c5.2xlarge	34	c4.2xlarge	31	0.9118
c5.4xlarge	68	c4.4xlarge	62	0.9118

Table 4: Scaling factor to account for processor differences

The scaled base cost per vCPU for the EBS-only c5 flavour class is shown in Table 5.

AWS Flavour	vCPUs	RAM (GiB)	EC2 Cost per hour (US\$)	Base cost per vCPU hour (US\$)	Scaled base cost per vCPU hour (US\$)	Scaled base cost per vCPU hour (AUD\$)
c5.large	2	4	0.111	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658
c5.xlarge	4	8	0.222	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658

Storage and compute workflow cost comparisons

c5.2xlarge	8	16	0.444	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658
c5.4xlarge	16	32	0.888	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658
c5.9xlarge	36	72	1.998	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658
c5.18xlarge	72	144	3.996	0.0555	0.0493	0.0658

Table 5: Base cost per GB-month to apply in determining AWS Awoonga estimate

Excluded costs

The cost estimates provided do not account for the following, which would apply to applications using commercial cloud:

- Data ingress or egress charges
- Data transfers between AWS storage tiers
- Minimum retention periods of data in AWS storage tiers
- Ensuring a specific network bandwidth to storage
- Ensuring a specific IOPS performance in Elastic Block Storage (QRIScloud provides 10 IOPS per vCPU)
- Use of QRIScloud's Special Compute (large memory or GPU nodes) above AWS m5a flavour pricing
- High performance scratch storage for high throughput computing workloads
- Member use of the national federated Object Storage service
- Service quality differences between QRIScloud and AWS.

Opportunities for AWS cost reduction

QCIF acknowledges that many research workloads could be re-engineered to use more economical AWS services, rather than the like-for-like services identified above.

Effort to transition to lower cost AWS services

Transitioning research workloads to use more economical AWS services, in most cases, would require experts who work with researchers to assess, plan, design, and execute the migration of their workloads.

Making an optimistic assumption that workload transition requires 2 weeks of engagement for each project, one expert could assist 24 projects over a 12-month period.

For every 100 projects to transition, four (4) experts would be required. At an estimated cost of \$120,000 per expert, the cost to transition 100 projects is likely to be around \$500,000.

With hundreds of existing projects, the people cost in transitioning to AWS services is significant.

Cloud compute

The cost of On-Demand virtual machine instances in AWS can be reduced by moving to Reserved Instances or the AWS Spot Market. For example, if it were possible to forecast demand with 100% accuracy, the use of Reserved Instances with 3 years and no up-front fees could reduce the total cost of cloud compute on AWS by up to 51%.

As it is not possible to forecast demand accurately, an appropriately sized reserve would need to be selected to optimise utilisation of Reserved Instances since any un-used capacity would still be charged. This would reduce the saving actually achieved.

The use of the Spot Market could lead to significantly greater savings in some cases, however not all research workloads are suited to using Spot Market. Spot instances can be shut down at short notice, making them unsuitable for always-on workloads, such as data portals. For those workloads that are suited to the use of Spot Market, effort may be required to design them such that they can be interrupted at any point and then resumed when there is available capacity at the nominated bid price.

Storage

To derive savings for data storage, whether on QRIScloud or elsewhere, the first step is to ensure that any data being stored is stored in an appropriate storage tier depending on its current use and life-cycle stage. Storing rarely accessed or archived data sets on a frequent access storage tier is both inefficient and expensive. Collections should be regularly curated and assessed by their custodians to ensure that the most appropriate storage tier is being used.

A switch from using file systems to object stores, such as S3, Glacier, and Deep Archive for storage in AWS, would reduce the at-rest costs for data, for example the at-rest costs for 1-petabyte of storage in Elastic File Storage is \$480,000 per month versus a cost of \$33,000 per month for S3. However, object stores will not be suitable for all workloads and the cost of transitioning workloads and codes to use object stores, rather than file systems, would need to be factored into any cost-benefit analysis. AWS charges for accessing data, moving data between storage tiers, and minimum charging periods (e.g. 180 days for Glacier Deep Archive) also need to be considered. Object stores would suit data that is “write-once, read-many”, such as reference or archived data sets.

High throughput computing

For high throughput compute workloads, particularly ones with light data payloads, Reserved Instances or the AWS Spot Market, will be more cost-effective than On-Demand instances. Similarly, as for cloud compute, an appropriate capacity would need to be determined if using Reserved Instances or workloads designed for interruption if using Spot Market.

AWS discount programs

Several discounting programs are available for AWS services, these include:

- Research data egress waiver program, which provides a discount of up to 15% of the total AWS invoice to offset against data egress charges.
- Enterprise agreements (at an institutional level)
- The whole-of-government agreement for AWS services as negotiated by the Digital Transformation Agency.

Workflow comparisons

Representative research workflows

QCIF has compared the costs of representative research workloads running on QRIScloud and AWS. The workflows used as a basis of comparison were:

- Biodiversity and Climate Change Virtual Laboratory
- ecocloud
- Galaxy Australia
- Data Muster
- TrISMA
- Bioplatforms Australia
- CQUniversity data archive
- James Cook University data archive
- HTC Genome Wide Assembly
- QCIF Members' use of QRIScloud.

A summary of the above comparisons are presented below, with a spreadsheet containing the data for these comparisons available at the following link:

<https://nextcloud.qriscloud.org.au/index.php/s/GYdnS8Qg89SWRpn>

Base estimate to run on AWS versus QRIScloud

Using actual consumption data, the following table presents the base¹ estimate cost for running the workloads on like-for-like AWS services as compared to QRIScloud.

Workflow	AWS Base Estimate		QRIScloud Estimate	
	2018	YTD 2019	2018	YTD 2019
BCCVL	\$122,114	\$75,501	\$62,654	\$38,730
ecocloud	\$18,410	\$27,141	\$9,454	\$13,754
Galaxy Australia				
GVL_Queensland	\$89,518	\$66,204	\$44,769	\$31,718
GenomicsVL	\$213,298	\$156,185	\$92,974	\$61,237
GenomicsVL_Devt	\$74,883	\$41,884	\$37,926	\$20,462
GenomicsVL_Students	\$74,081	\$26,475	\$37,280	\$13,069
TOTAL	\$451,780	\$290,748	\$212,949	\$126,486
Data Muster	\$9,127	\$6,801	\$4,690	\$3,495
TrISMA	\$72,798	\$24,845	\$37,410	\$12,768
CQU Archive			\$1,740	\$3,136
Base	\$26,131	\$47,090		
Convert to use Glacier	\$2,419	\$4,360		
JCU Archive			\$21,165	\$12,752
Base	\$317,815	\$191,484		
Convert to use Glacier	\$29,427	\$17,730		

¹Additional costs will be incurred above these base levels for items listed in the Excluded Costs section. QCIF's calculation excludes these costs— however depending on project workload they could add a significant percentage to overall costs.

Storage and compute workflow cost comparisons

Actual costs on AWS versus QRIScloud estimate

The following workloads use, or did use, commercial cloud. The actual commercial cloud costs are presented with an estimate of the equivalent QRIScloud costs.

Workflow	AWS Actual	QRIScloud Estimate
Bioplatforms Australia	\$15,014	\$11,202
HTC GWAS	\$31,600	\$3,758

Estimates for QCIF Members' consumption

The following base¹ estimate costs for AWS take actual QCIF Member's consumption and costs them using like-for-like AWS services.

Period	Frequent Access Storage	Infrequent Access Storage	Cloud Compute	Volume Storage	Awoonga HTC	AWS Estimate	QRIScloud Estimate
2018	27,977,318	1,859,494	2,462,635	105,591	396,892	32,801,930	2,862,312
Q1, 2019	8,439,890	486,752	608,283	38,216	124,305	9,697,446	793,574

The following base¹ estimate costs for AWS take actual QCIF Member's consumption and costs them using more economical AWS services, specifically:

- S3 rather than EFS Standard for Frequent Access storage
- AWS Glacier rather than EFS Infrequent Access for Infrequent Access storage
- EC2 3-year reserved instances rather than EC2 On-Demand for virtual machines.

Period	Frequent Access Storage	Infrequent Access Storage	Cloud Compute	Volume Storage	Awoonga HTC	AWS Estimate	QRIScloud Estimate
2018	1,787,440	172,175	1,208,515	105,591	396,892	3,670,613	2,862,312
Q1, 2019	539,215	45,070	298,509	38,216	124,305	1,045,315	793,574

These base estimates do not account for the time, effort, and skill required to re-engineer workloads to use the more economical AWS services.

Issues and barriers to goals

There are several items of note that present challenges when attempting to calculate storage and compute workflow cost comparisons. These include:

1. There are a range of commercial cloud costs that are obfuscated, making it difficult to accurately predict the true cost of a workload. However, it is possible to determine a minimum base estimate of cost for commercial services to use as a point of comparison against the cost of in-house services.
2. Determining the quantum of difference between the base estimate cost and the actual cost can only be made after running actual or representative workload on commercial cloud services.
3. Any estimates and cost comparisons are valid for a point-in-time. Cost comparisons need to be regularly adjusted to factor in changes to internal and external variables.
4. There is not always a like-for-like service to use as a basis of comparison between commercial services and in-house services. Any approach taken for making a comparison needs to account for this in some way.

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QCIF Technical Working Group

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Jason Bell (CQUni)
Ashley Wright (QUT)
Harry Butler (USQ)
Paul Jardine (GU)
David Green (UQ)
Peter Embleton (USC)

QCIF eResearch Analysts

Chantelle Pinnington (JCU)
Jason Bell (CQU)
Jason D'Netto (QUT)
Francis Gacenga (USQ)
Amanda Miotto (GU)
Nick Hamilton (UQ)
Marlies Hankel (UQ)

QCIF SISC and Board Members

Malcolm Wolski (GU)
Shaune Sinclair (CQUni)
David Abramson (UQ)
Lyndon Christian (QUT)
Francis Gacenga (USQ)
Erin Rayment (USQ)
Matthew Bellgard (QUT)

Additional QCIF member engagement

Jake Carroll (UQ)
Eric Hornsby (UQ)
David Abramson (UQ)
Michael Mallon (UQ)
Martin Nicholls (UQ)
Hamish Macintosh (QUT)
Heidi Perrett (GU/QCIF)
Grahame Bowland (QCIF)
Nigel Ward (QCIF)
Hoylen Sue (QCIF)
Mohammad Hassan (UQ)
David Stockdale (UQ)

Amazon

David Freeman
Avi Lewin